

PULP AND PAPER PRODUCTION FROM WAST COMBS

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Abstract

Mankind has always investigated the ways of communicating and recording their thoughts and how to improve these. The first examples of these are waxed boards, leaves, bronze, silk, and clay tablets. Saving a large amount of information and the paper circulation from hand to hand cheaply have not been possible until the paper invention.

The aim of the study was to investigate suitability of wasp combs for manufacturing pulp and paper. For this reason, soda-oxygen cooking method was used for producing pulp and paper. Then, pulp yield and physical and optical properties of pulp and paper were determined.

As the obtained result showed that, wasp combs were suitable for pulp and paper production. It was possible to manufacture high quality paper by mixing with wood and annual plants fibers.

Key words: wasp, soda-oxygen, pulp, paper, comb

Introduction

Wasp combs are accepted as the first paper produced from wood fibers and wasps are recognized as the first paper-makers by researchers (Tutuş, 2012). Wasps eat bark and wood, chew for a long time and set their combs in wall hole, tree caverns using bark and wood fibers. Combs have thin layers like paper produced from lignocellulosic materials. Its structure is thick, coarse, yellowish-brown and decayed wood fibers. (Hunt, 1996; Tolon, 1999).

Figure 1: Wasp Combs (URL-1, 2013).

Paper is an important product for development of science and culture. The first money

logic was to buy and exchange somethings so paper was the starting point of such financial things. Today, paper is one of the leading industry products and most needed in daily life. It is used in scientific studies, education and institutions, printing, writing and publication activities, as well as money, packaging and kitchen (URL-2, 2013).

The objective of the study was to investigate wasp combs suitability for producing pulp and paper. Therefore, a soda-oxygen cooking was performed to wasp combs. Then, pulp yield and optical and physical properties of wasp combs' pulp were determined.

Material and Method

The raw material (wasp combs) used in this study was provided from Osmaniye-Turkey.

Soda-oxygen cooking method was used in pulp production from wasp combs. Combs were kept in hot water 24 hours, then samples were filtered, cleaned and placed in polyethylene bag 24 hours for stabilize moisture content.

After being prepared cooking liquors quantities shown Table 1, cooking experiments were made in an electrically heated laboratory rotary digester of 15 liters capacity and maximum pressure of 25 kg/cm². All pulps were washed and screened on a 0.15 mm slotted screen. At the end of screening, the pulp was pressed up to 20-25% dryness. Later on, moisture content of pulps regulated to 20-25% and placed in polyethylene bags and moisture content was determined. Handsheets with grammage of 70 g/m² were made on a Rapid Kothen machine.

Table 1. Cooking conditions with soda-oxygen method of wasp combs

NaOH ratio(%)	8
Oxygen Pressure (bar)	5
Temperature (°C)	100
Time (min)	25
Solution / combs oranı	20/1

Physical and optical properties of handsheets were measured according to Tappi Standart Test Methods given below.

- Breaking Length: H.E Messmer, Testometric 220M (Anonymous, 1992)
- Tear Index: Elmendorf Tearing Tester (Anonymous, 1992)
- Burst Index: B.F. Perkins & Son, Mullen Tester (Anonymous, 1992)
- Brightness, Whiteness, Yellowness and Opacity: Datacolor Elrepho (Anonymous, 1997).

compared with wheat straw and cotton pulps and paper in Table 2.

Breaking length and burst index of short fiber pulps and papers obtained from wasp combs were lower than other annual plants'. Therefore, unbleached and bleached pulps produced from wasp combs can be mixed with long fiber pulps and used in all kinds paper production.

Wasp combs pulps can be used in the production of printing and writing papers as well as in newspaper and packing papers by the mixture long fibrous materials.

Result and Discussion

Pulp yield, physical and optical properties of pulps and paper produced from wasp combs were

Table 2. Pulp yields and physical and optical properties of pulp and paper produced from wasp combs and some annual plants.

Raw Material	Screened Yield (%)	Screen Reject (%)	Total Yield (%)	Breaking Length (m)	Burst Index (kPam ² /g)	Opacity (% ISO)	Brightness (% ISO)	Yellowness (E 313)
Wasp Comb	38.35	0.59	38.94	3452	1.15	98.65	20.49	40.60
Wheat Straw	46.07	2.25	48.32	6240	4.56	99.04	62.40	27.54
Cotton Straw	40.05	3.25	43.30	3854	1.65	97.07	20.25	38.27
Kraft	-	-	-	3880	2.17	99.56	18.99	51.95
%75 Kraft-%25 Wasp Comb	-	-	-	2974	1.86	98.93	20.15	53.03
%50 Kraft-%50 Wasp Comb	-	-	-	2890	1.75	99.36	21.39	48.59
%25 Kraft-%75 Wasp Comb	-	-	-	2632	1.70	99.89	22.19	45.83

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